

Atlantic Ecosystems Assessment, Forecasting & Sustainability

Deliverable number 9.4

AtlantECO Communication activities and performance indicators

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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

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1 Version History

Table 1: Version history of the deliverable

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
0.1	Eva-Salomé Romano	Initial draft	20/11/25
0.2	Andre Abreu	Review, contributions	20/12/25
0.3	Eva-Salome Romano, Andre Abreu	Review, formatting	20/01/26
0.4	Andre Abreu	Final version	05/02/26
1.0	Stéphane Pesant	Review for Submission	20/02/26

2 Executive summary

2.1 Scope and purpose of the deliverable

D9.4: AtlantECO Communication activities and performance indicators [M48]

This document presents the final report on the communication activities carried out throughout the project, including performance indicators per media type. The performance metrics presented in this report are based on compiled annual reports, presented at the project's annual meetings, which have been consolidated into this final deliverable for the end of the project. The Introduction and Conclusion sections provide overarching reflections on the key challenges encountered as well as the main successes achieved during the whole journey of AtlantECO communication activities.

2.2 Summary, content and links for complete metrics

- Communication plan : [LINK](#)
- Communication process : [LINK](#)
- Podcast
 - 55 episodes.
 - +2600 plays.
 - Top five best-performing episodes
 - Episode 1 - The story of the AtlantECO project (164 plays).
 - Episode 18 - Understanding the impact of the Namibian desert on the marine microbiome (129 plays).
 - Episode 44 - Exploring plankton biodiversity (103 plays).
 - Episode 2 - Science of AtlantECO: Marine Microbiome (91 plays).
 - Episode 3 - Science of AtlantECO: Seascape and connectivity (81 plays).
 - Available from here:
 - <https://www.atlanteco.eu/podcast>
 - <https://shows.acast.com/atlanteco-podcast>
 - Follow up document : [LINK](#)
- Infography
 - Overview of the AtlantECO project : [LINK](#)
 - Mission Microbiomes : [LINK](#)
- Booklet
 - AtlantECO presentation booklet : [LINK](#)
 - Q&A English version : [LINK](#)
 - Q&A Portuguese version : [LINK](#)
- Videos
 - Presentation : [LINK](#)

- AtlantECO General Assembly in Vigo : [LINK](#)
- Outreach in the AtlantECO project : [LINK](#)
- AtlantECO Hackathon : [LINK](#)

- Social Media
 - Youtube
 - Page : [LINK](#)
 - 89 subscribers.
 - 8 500 total views (53% of long videos, 45% of shorts, 2% of lives).
 - Over 212 hours of total viewing time.
 - Over 48 000 total impressions.
 - 113 pieces of content : 95 videos, 14 shorts, 4 live streams.
 - Top five best-performing videos
 - Episode 55 of the podcast [LINK](#) (1800 views).
 - Episode 54 of the podcast [LINK](#) (1000 views).
 - Project presentation video [LINK](#) (+650 views).
 - Episode 53 of the podcast [LINK](#) (+550 views).
 - Amazon plumes during Mission Microbiomes [LINK](#) (+250 views).

- Website
 - Total users: 489
 - Average time per session: 4minutes 9seconds
 - Pageviews 3200
 - Traffic type
 - Direct 54,9%
 - Organic 33,6%
 - Referral 6,3%
 - Social 5,2%
 - Top 5 countries of total website traffic
 - Portugal 19%
 - France 12%
 - Italy 11%
 - Spain 9%
 - UK 8%

Infographics produced for the project

Layout of Instagram's publication.

3 Introduction

In 2018, the European Commission launched the *All Atlantic flagship* program with the *Belem Declaration*, presented by the former EU Commissioner for Research and Innovation and by the President of Portugal, in the beautiful and historical Belem Tower in Lisbon. By that time, the “Atlantic research community” was still limited to sectoral programs and with a vast majority of active research institutions based in the northern hemisphere. The “All Atlantic” concept was then created to bridge this gap and foster collaboration with southern countries, focusing on Brazil and South Africa.

Following the call for projects, the challenges identified by project's proponents were diverse, but one seemed more important and considered by the majority of proposals: the lack of modern and integrated physical, chemical and biological data from the South Atlantic basin. Considering biological data, especially from areas beyond national jurisdictions, this gap appeared even bigger, with a poor representation of samples coming from the south when compared with the North Atlantic.

Bridging this “Southern Gap” was then a strong basis for the AtlantECO proposal. Bringing together institutions and research vessels from various countries, including many from Brazil and South Africa, in order to cover a maximum of important regions in the South Atlantic, was the main target for the community involved in the proposal. With this in mind, AtlantECO project was built on three main pillars, addressing innovative issues still poorly studied:

- The Seascape, an innovative concept aiming to bring attention to the importance of ocean circulation and connectivity
- The Plastisphere, or the permanent changes in ecosystems due to increasing presence of plastics particles
- The Ocean Microbiome, a largely unexplored trove of microorganisms, containing strong potential for biodiscoveries and for knowledge generation on the ocean ecosystems.

Associated with the main pillars, case studies and core regions were defined, in order to involve various stakeholders and industry representatives, as well as decision makers and institutions.

Based on these general concepts, FTO and project partners built the AtlantECO Communication Strategy, firstly exploring in each of the main pillars what could be the better “entry doors” for the general public understanding, in order to insure societal impact and legacy. Climate Change, Plastic Pollution, Biodiscoveries, among some others, were then identified as powerful drivers for reaching public attention and stakeholders participation.

As the first step of the Communication Strategy, we built the AtlantECO Communication Kit, with the creation of a website, social media, a project video, a project folder and a set of infographics. The main challenge for the communication tools was to present the Atlantic Ocean Ecosystem, its importance, its complexity and interactions with the Blue Economy, linking this general vision to the main pillars of the project. Also, all materials were translated into Portuguese for Brazilian partners and future use by local stakeholders.

After the launching of the Communication Kit, some further tools and developments were proposed during the first two years of the project, aiming to feed the Flagship Cruises' Port Calls, especially with *RV Tara*, a sailing vessel with a charismatic shape that has attracted visitors, media and partners since its launching in 2003. During *Tara's Mission Microbiomes (2020-2022)*, covering the South Atlantic and Antarctica, more than ten public Port Calls were proposed in Brazil, Argentina, South Africa, Namibia, Angola, Congo, Senegal and France. For each Port Call, the Communication Kit was deployed, with an exhibit based on the infographics, a set of videos made onboard *Tara*, and science talks always organised with local institutions. We also proposed conferences and policy events in key cities like Rio de Janeiro or Cape Town.

Navigating the COVID pandemics

After the project launch, partners had to adapt to the COVID pandemics rules, which represented a serious challenge for the project, especially for the flagship cruises. Costs of port fees exploded, the crew was not allowed to disembark in Brazil, the export of samples became a nightmare, among other challenges. For the communication strategy, it forced some adaptations, with remote events and digital content being proposed, which in some cases were quite successful, as the series of podcasts that worked really well, and for which we had a very nice reach for a scientific project.

Outreach Conference in Salvador de Bahia, Brazil.

4 Content

4.1 Social Media

The AtlantECO project’s social media strategy initially covered multiple platforms from September 2020.

- Instagram : Launched in September 2020.
- Facebook : Launched in September 2020.
- Youtube : Launched in September 2020.
- LinkedIn (professional page): Launched on November 24, 2024.
- Twitter/X : The Twitter account has been closed in 2025 due to political considerations, shifting focus entirely to other platforms.

Current follower totals (November 2025):

- LinkedIn: 623 followers.
- YouTube: 89 followers.
- Instagram: 1017 followers.
- Facebook: 119 followers.

LinkedIn performance analysis (december 2024 - october 2025)

Table 2: LinkedIn interactions analysis

year/month	impressions	likes	Comments	Reposts	Total interactions
2024/12	380	13	0	1	14
2025/01	1,378	25	1	13	39
2025/02	2,501	51	8	10	69
2025/03	11,772	152	3	65	220
2025/04	488	8	0	4	12
2025/05	998	16	0	6	22
2025/06	549	11	0	3	14
2025/07	1,823	34	3	14	51
2025/08	1,143	23	0	4	27
2025/09	743	18	1	5	24
2025/10	785	28	0	4	32

Across the reporting period, the project’s LinkedIn account performance showed a clear growth trajectory followed by a strong peak and a period of consolidation with sustained engagement.

Following the account launch, December 2024 recorded modest activity with 380 impressions and 14 total interactions (13 likes, 1 repost). The performance increased in January 2025 (1378 impressions, 39

interactions) and continued through February 2025 (2051 impressions, 69 interactions), reflecting steady engagement. March 2025 marked the peak performance month, generating 11772 impressions and 220 impressions, driven by a high-performing post (see top 3 below). After this peak, activity declined in April (488 impressions, lowest interaction count of 12), before recovering in May (998 impressions, 22 interactions) and June (549 impressions, 14 interactions). Growth resumed in July (1823 impressions, 51 interactions), followed by stable engagement levels through August to October: impressions ranged from 743 to 1143 and total interactions remained constant, ranging between 24 and 32.

Table 3: Top three best-performing LinkedIn publications

Rank	Publication Date	Total Interactions	Impressions	Visual
1	03/14/2025	99 (71 Likes, 1 Comment, 27 Reposts)	8024	
2	03/21/2025	64 (45 Likes, 0 Comments, 19 Reposts)	1673	
3	07/04/2025	51 (34 Likes, 3 Comments, 14 Reposts)	1823	

Youtube performance analysis (september 2020 - october 2025)

The channel currently hosts a total of 113 contents.

Table 4: YouTube channel's cumulative metrics

Metric	Value	Interpretation
Total subscribers	89	Niche community
Total impressions	48K	High reach : the algorithm is recommending content widely.
Total views	8500	Very healthy number of views relative to the subscriber base (approximately 95 views per subscriber).
Total watch Time	212 hours	Excellent engagement
Total content	113	95 long videos, 14 shorts, and 4 live streams.

Shorts are an excellent driver for views and potentially impressions, but the long-form videos (53% of views) are responsible for generating the majority of the high watch time, which is valuable for the channel.

Table 5: Top five best-performing videos

Rank	Views	Content	
1	1800	Podcast episode 55	

Rank	Views	Content	
2	1000	Podcast episode 54	<p>Episode 54 - Modelling the ocean ...</p> <p>1 k vues</p>
3	+650	Video presentation	<p>AtlantECO- Overview of the project</p> <p>689 vues • il y a 4 ans</p>

Rank	Views	Content	
4	+550	Podcast episode 53	<p>Podcast</p> <p>and also</p> <p>Studying Ecological networks: why is it ...</p> <p>559 vues</p>
5	+250	Amazon plumes during Mission Microbiomes	<p>in order to understand the link between the land, the river and the Atlantic Ocean</p> <p>Mission Microbiomes: Sampling the Amazon and its plume, September 2021</p> <p>270 vues • il y a 4 ans</p>

Instagram performance analysis (september 2020 - october 2025)

We currently have 173 posts and 1018 followers on the Instagram account.

Table 6: Yearly Instagram output and impressions

Year	number of publications	total impressions
2021	25	182
2022	54	632
2023	7	141
2024	47	16346
2025	37	16122

Here is the post that performed best for each year :

2021 : Crosspost video with @veleiroeco (111 likes).

2022 : World Microbiome Day (166 likes).

2023 : World Maritime Day (74 likes).

2024 : Crosspost with @oceanliteracy_unesco (174 likes).

2025 : Look back on the Final Scientific Conference of the AtlantECO project (45 likes).

Conclusion on Instagram :

Over the past five years, the project has built a community of 1018 followers on Instagram around this European project, AtlantECO, reflecting sustained interest in the initiative. To broaden reach and visibility, content was regularly cross-posted in collaboration with other organisations, to raise awareness through other channels. The content strategy combined explanatory, contemplative, and promotional videos, including dedicated posts to support the project's podcast on YouTube. Content documenting the expedition, explanatory posts about the expedition's missions, and educational posts on ocean knowledge - informed by contributions from the expedition's scientists - were shared to support engagement and knowledge diffusion.

Layout of Instagram's publication.

“Max Plancton” Video produced in Brazil for outreach / @Hugo Sarmento, UFSCAR

4.2 Website

A new AtlantECO legacy website was created for the final conference of the project and will be augmented in 2026 to present the Key Exploitable Results of the project. The old domain name of the project website will point to the new legacy website, which will be maintained by the current project management partner (TRUST-IT) for two years after the end of the project. The augmented content will be presented in the final report of the project and during the final review meeting.

<https://atlanteco-legacy.eu/>

5 Conclusion

After more than five years of work, AtlantECO resembled a huge community of scientists, early-career researchers, policy experts, communication experts, ocean passionate individuals, as well as local stakeholders and political institutions. Through the project, the concept of an All Atlantic Community made its way towards a concrete community, with thousands of people that are now connected in some way. In collaboration with Sister projects, with AANCHOR coordination project and later with the AAORIA alliance, AtlantECO actions has been always advocating for the vision of a Healthy Atlantic, with a Sustainable Blue Economy and resilient ecosystems.

For FTO, it was a challenge and an exciting journey to lead the communication and outreach activities of the whole AtlantECO consortium. The positive results and the impact for the future of the All Atlantic Community are in our hearts and minds, but also clearly knowledgeable in the numbers and KPIs detailed for each stream of action presented in this Deliverable. We will never forget special moments we lived through this journey, like the *Tara's* Belem Port Call, with the boat docked in the most lively part of the City center, or the successful Science to Policy Conference in Rio de Janeiro in the beautiful Museu do Amanha, or the amazing interactions and summer school with the Africans young researchers in Cape Town.

Tara and Veleiro ECO in Itajai, Brazil

As a final conclusion, we would like to mention the incredible opportunity to work on a long term basis with Brazilian and South African researchers and institutions. The possibility to allocate funding for southern partners for many years was key to create a resilient community of researchers and passionate Atlantic citizens. We sincerely believe that the results, data collection and knowledge production emerging from the different All Atlantic sister projects already represents an historical milestone for science and the Blue citizenship in the South Atlantic.

Project partners onboard Veleiro ECO in Brazil

AtlantECO team onboard in Brazil